

1 **Peptidyl prolyl isomerase (PPI) family genes are intrinsically linked with homeostasis.**

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6 Peptidyl prolyl isomerases are cyclophilins with established functions in cell death.

7 Citations

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9 Sayen, M.R., Gottlieb, R.A., Dorn, G.W. and Robbins, J., 2005. Loss of cyclophilin D reveals a critical role
10 for mitochondrial permeability transition in cell death. *Nature*, 434(7033), pp.658-662.